

Agile creation of multi-layer corpora with corpus-tools.org

Stephan Druskat, Thomas Krause, Carolin Odebrecht
Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin

Agile corpus creation

Agile corpus creation (ACC) (Voormann & Gut, 2008): A paradigm shift, replacing traditionally linear phases of the corpus creation process with **cyclic iterations** of

- Corpus querying
- Annotation schema development
- Corpus annotation
- Corpus analysis

Query-driven: “[E]arly corpus queries constitute an evaluation of the annotation process” (ibid., p. 243).

Why agile corpus creation?

ACC helps overcome the trade-off between corpus size, and annotation quantity and quality.

“Traditional” linear workflow:

Schema > Annotation > Query/Analysis
ACC: query-initial phase-cycle (cf. graphic)

- ⊕ Schema/annotation errors caught early
- ⊕ Constant evaluation of annotation process
- ⊕ Bottom-up process, minimal initial requirements

Agile, **true multi-layer** corpus creation requires:

- ⊕ Multi-layer, **multi-concept** annotation tool (Atomic)
- ⊕ Powerful multi-layer search beyond values (ANNIS)

Multi-layer annotation: Atomic

Atomic (Druskat et al., 2014): a multi-layer corpus annotation platform, currently in development (github.com/infraling/atomic).

- Uses the generic **Salt** data model (Zipser & Romary, 2010)
 - ⊕ “multi-concept”: Allows for arbitrary annotation concepts
- Embeds the **Pepper** conversion tool (Zipser et al., 2011)
 - ⊕ Facilitates compatibility with a large number of tools
- Currently provides a generic multi-layer annotation editor
- **Extensible** through plugins (Eclipse RCP)
 - ⊕ New multi-layer editors can be added at any time
- Currently no search capabilities

Multi-layer search: graphANNIS

graphANNIS (Krause et al., forthcoming): a new, C++-based implementation (github.com/thomaskrause/graphANNIS) of ANNIS (Krause & Zeldes, 2016).

- Main memory graph database
 - ⊕ Removes the need to install a relational database
- Already supports a large subset of AQL, the ANNIS Query Language
- Closely aligned with the Salt data model
- Self-contained library
- Can be embedded in other tools and pipelines
 - ⊕ Facilitates agility through combination with other tools

Prototype integration of graphANNIS in Atomic

Our prototypical integration of graphANNIS in Atomic enables agile multi-layer, multi-concept corpus creation in a single tool.

- graphANNIS provides an API for corpus and document management (C++)
- The C++ API is wrapped in Java with JavaCPP (github.com/bytedeco/javacpp)
- This Java wrapper is used to build an OSGi bundle, shared on Maven Central
- As Atomic plugins are OSGi bundles, graphANNIS can now be integrated in Atomic which facilitates the current feature set:
 - Complex, linguistically informed search via the ANNIS Query Language, i.e., users do not need to learn another QL if they know ANNIS
 - Fast indexing of live corpus data via the graphANNIS main memory model
 - A graphical user interface for AQL search queries
 - Open search results with annotation editors in Atomic

Conclusion and outlook

The integration of graphANNIS in Atomic enables users to conveniently apply query-driven, agile corpus creation workflows, and supports re-use of existing corpora. This will be consolidated by some of the planned features, e.g.:

- Implement application of console commands to search results (“semi-automatic annotation”, cf. GraphAnno (Gast et al., 2015)).
- Embed AQL search directly in editors, e.g., to find more instances of a selected linguistic structure within the same corpus.

References

- Druskat, Stephan, Lennart Bierkandt, Volker Gast, Christoph Rzymiski & Florian Zipser. 2014. Atomic: an open-source software platform for multi-level corpus annotation. In Proceedings of the 12th Konferenz zur Verarbeitung natürlicher Sprache (KONVENS 2014), 228–234. Hildesheim, Germany.
- Gast, Volker, Lennart Bierkandt & Christoph Rzymiski. 2015. Annotating modals with GraphAnno, a configurable lightweight tool for multi-level annotation. In Proceedings of the workshop on models for modality annotation, 19–28. Stroudsburg, PA.
- Krause, Thomas, Ulf Leser & Anke Lüdeling. forthcoming. graphANNIS: A fast query engine for deeply annotated linguistic corpora. Journal of Language Technology and Computational Linguistics (Special Issue on Korpuslinguistische Softwarewerkzeuge).
- Krause, Thomas & Amir Zeldes. 2016. ANNIS3: A new architecture for generic corpus query and visualization. Digital Scholarship in the Humanities 31(1), 118–139. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/dsh/31.1.118>.
- Voormann, Holger & Ulrike Gut. 2008. Agile corpus creation. Corpus Linguistics and Linguistic Theory 4(2), 235–251. doi:10.1515/CLLT.2008.010.
- Zipser, Florian & Laurent Romary. 2010. A model oriented approach to the mapping of annotation formats using standards. In Proceedings of the Workshop on Language Resource and Language Technology Standards, Seventh International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation (LREC 2010), Valletta, Malta.
- Zipser, Florian, Amir Zeldes, Julia Ritz, Laurent Romary & Ulf Leser. 2011. Pepper: Handling a multiverse of formats. Poster presented at 33. Jahrestagung der Deutschen Gesellschaft für Sprachwissenschaft, 24 February, Göttingen University, Göttingen, Germany.